

Complement–Adjunct Non-Distinction in Prepositional Phrases: A Study of Educated Nigerian Speakers of English

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Abstract

'Adjunct' and 'complement' denote grammatical functions realisable by prepositional phrases (PPs) among other structural elements of language. The (in)appropriate distinction between these functions may hinder or facilitate accurate meaning interpretation. This study investigated the linguistic knowledge of educated Nigerian speakers of English regarding whether PPs function as complements or adjuncts in specific syntactic contexts. Using Chomsky's (1970) X-bar framework as the theoretical basis, data were collected from 450 educated Nigerian speakers of English through three grammaticality judgement tasks. These tasks included the Structure Recognition Test (SRT), the Function Determination Test (FDT), and the Complement–Adjunct Ordering Test (C-AOT). Participants were selected through stratified random sampling from university undergraduates and graduates holding BA, BSc, MA, and PhD degrees. Analysis of the responses indicates that the participants generally could not distinguish between the complement and adjunct functions of PPs in the sentences provided. Although the participants performed relatively well in the SRT and were able to identify prepositional phrases, recording a facilitation index of 72.4%, they showed limited ability to determine whether the identified PPs functioned as complements or adjuncts, or to order complement and adjunct PPs appropriately. In the Function Determination Test, only 210 participants correctly assigned the appropriate function to the PP in Test Item 3, representing the highest performance score of 46.6% recorded in that test. Performance in the Complement–Adjunct Ordering Test was similarly poor, with only 32% of participants correctly ordering complement and adjunct PPs, as indicated in Table 3 (Test Item 3). Further analysis revealed violations of English word-order restrictions. A clear example is the participants' inability to place adjunct PPs after

complement PPs in Test Items 1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9. The poor performance by subjects in Test 3 may be attributed to the fact that the subjects possess zero grammaticality judgement intuition about ordering restrictions in English, especially the rule which stipulates that complements occur closer to their associated heads than adjuncts.

Keywords: Adjunct, Complement, Word Order Prepositional Phrase (PP), grammaticality judgement intuition.

1. Introduction

Sentences (1–4) contain prepositional phrases (PPs) in English which appear to share a similar structural status, namely P + NP (cf. Brown and Miller 1980, 1982; Radford 1988, 1997; Poole 2002; Aarts 2001; Yule 2007). However, the grammatical relations expressed by the bracketed PPs in sentences (1) and (2) differ from those expressed by the PPs in sentences (3) and (4).

- (1) They sing [in the choir]
- (2) Eunice might be going [to the supermarket] PP
- (3) Dara will bake the cake [for the party] PP
- (4) He carried the animal home [on his shoulders]

The bracketed constituents in (1-4) can, at some level of structure, be described as strings of the same schematic form as in (5) below:

- (5) PP → P+NP

The bracketed PPs in (1) and (2) are complements while those in (3) and (4) are adjuncts.

Sentences in language are built out of words and phrases, each of which belongs to a specific grammatical category, and serves a specific grammatical function within the sentence containing it (cf. Radford, 1997, Aarts, 2001). For example, the noun “man” serves different roles in each of the sentences in (6):

- (6) a. The man speaks with a drawl
- b. George gives the man an upkeep every month.

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In sentence (6a), “man” is the subject in the sentence containing it. In sentence (6b), “man” is the indirect object of the verb “gives”. Thus, in English, nouns can perform the functions subject, object or complement (Aarts, 2001, Adger, 2002, and others).

Similarly, PPs function variously in English. Like any linguistic form, they can fill different roles: *subject*, *complement* or *adjunct*, just like the noun mentioned earlier. However, there is a salient function for any one linguistic form. Appropriate use of a language, whether in speech or in writing, requires that a language user be conversant with the various functions which the structural units of the relevant language are capable of realising in relevant syntactic contexts. For example, the analysis of the noun 'man' in (6) above as a subject in (6)(a) and indirect object in (6)(a) demonstrates the function which the same word is capable of performing in different sentence contexts. The terms '*subject*' and '*indirect object*' are functional labels. In the same vein, '*complement*' and '*adjunct*' are functional labels realisable by various structural units like prepositional phrases – our focus of investigation in this study. Thus, the structural unit PP with the schematic form PP→P+NP is capable of realising/filling complement or adjunct roles in relevant syntactic contexts. Complement PPs and Adjunct PPs are semantically distinctive in use.

The term '*adjunct*' is a functional label realisable by linguistic/structural forms such as adverbs/adverbials or prepositional phrases. In a somewhat restricted sense, '*adjunct*' refers to the grammatical function of a constituent that specifies the '*how*', '*when*', '*where*', or '*why*' of the situation expressed by a sentence (Aarts, 2001, p. 113). Adjuncts are similar in status to subjects in that they denote grammatical function (cf. Brown and Miller, 1980, Radford, 1988, Adger, 2002, etc.). They are generally considered to be peripheral because they are not seen as nuclear members of the clause; however, they fill some semantic roles despite being more peripheral than participants – that is, subjects and objects.

They detail such pieces of information as relate to matters of settings, temporal and physical, or the manner in which the process of the clause is implemented (Bloor and Bloor, 2004, p. 131). Adjuncts further provide information about 'the people or other entities which accompany the process rather than directly engage in it' (ibid).

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Adjuncts are not arguments of V-heads and hence are more peripheral to heads than the immediately following material, which is an argument. Within the X-bar framework adopted in the present investigation, adjuncts are sisters of the single-bar level above the head, that is, sisters of *XI* that dominates the head (*X*). In some sentence contexts, adjuncts can be right- or left-hand sisters to *XI* (Radford, 1988; Carnie, 2007, 2011). Adjuncts are characterised by the ability to be “stacked” over one another and can be reordered quite easily. However, the mobility principle applicable to adjuncts does not permit them to disrupt the close syntactic bond between a complement and its head. Adjuncts are generally optional constituents within sentence structure.

Complement is another functional category which is part of the focus of the present study. It is similar in status to “subject”, “object”, and “adjunct” just discussed. A complement makes the meaning of a lexical head (*X*) more specific. This is why it occurs very close to the head so that nothing can intervene between them. Various structural units serve a complementary function, for instance, nouns, PPs, AdjPs and clauses.

Within the X-bar format, adjuncts are both sisters and daughters of X-bar, and complements are sisters of *X* and daughters of X-bar. To simplify this a little, adjuncts resemble complements in that both are daughters of X-bar, but they differ from complements in that adjuncts are sisters of X-bar, whereas complements are sisters of *X* (Radford, 1988). The figure below offers a clearer picture of the places of attachment of adjuncts and complements in the tree configuration of the NP “the book of poems with a red cover”.

Fig.1: Tree Configuration of the phrase: “the book of poems with a red cover”.

From the figure above, it can be observed that the two PPs “of poems” and “with a red cover” are not attached to the same nodes, nor is their proximity to the head N the same: the PP that fills the complement role is closer to the head “book” than the PP “with a red cover”, which serves an adjunct function. It can be observed also that adjuncts are optional constituents of a clause; they (as illustrated in Fig. 1 above) occur at the periphery and so are omissible and mobile. Complements do not enjoy mobility as adjuncts do.

One major aspect of the domain of inquiry of this study is the order of words/constituents in sentences. Words/constituents are not strung together in random fashion (cf. Aarts, 2001; Carnie, 2008). The rules of sentence construction include rules which specify way(s) words/constituents are ordered. For example, the string in (7) is possible and grammatical, but (8) and (9) are not:

- (7) The student ate a meat-pie.
- (8) The ate a meat pie student
- (9) Meat-pie student the ate a.

The contrast between (7) and (8) does not only show a difference in the ordering of the words in the sentences but also implicates certain issues of syntax and its relationship with meaning interpretation and communicative effectiveness. In English,

the word which denotes the activity of eating (*ate*) must (according to the rules of English syntax) precede the word (or string of words) which refers to the entity that was being eaten (a meat pie). A further observation when (7) and (8) are compared is that not only must 'ate' occur before 'a meat-pie', but it has to be ensured that the two elements 'the' and 'a' precede the words 'student' and 'meat-pie', respectively.

These ordering principles also apply in syntactic contexts where there are two PPs in one sentence. In such situations, the PP which serves an adjunct function is ordered after the one which fills a complement function. Grammatical (syntactic) competence relies heavily on the organising principles of particular languages. However, a large L2 syntax of English has shown that Word Order (WO) rules are often glossed over; hence, inappropriate syntactic output often results. In Nigeria, a nonnative English context, usage has been shown to contain deviant syntactic structures (cf. Adesanonye, 1975; Kujore, 1985; Jowitt, 1991; Udoudom, 2011; etc.). Thus, this study seeks to determine specifically the (in)ability of Nigerian L2 users of English in distinguishing prepositional phrases which function as complements from those which serve as adjuncts.

2. Literature Review

Ekah (1998) adopts the X-bar format to analyse the noun phrase in Ibibio. According to the author, NPs in Ibibio are built out of an obligatory N head, pre-modifiers and post-modifiers. A further issue handled in Ekah (1988) is the process by which different noun types are derived. Some of the processes include agentive nominalisation, instrumental nominalisation, gerundive nominalisation and reduplicative nominalisation. These nominalisation processes are significant in terms of the types of nouns they derive, as nouns differ from other word classes in their complement structure.

An important aspect of Ekah (1998) is the idea that N-heads in Ibibio subcategorise complements and adjuncts at different levels of projection. Moreover, the source observes that there is structural affinity between complements and their associated heads, such an affinity is not observed to exist between lexical heads and adjuncts. The work concludes that the NP in Ibibio contains an intermediate (or small nominal) phrase, the N-bar (or *NI* or *N*). Phrase Structure Grammar (PSG) lacks the descriptive power to account for such intermediate structures.

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Radford (1988) elaborately discusses vital aspects of complementation such as complement order, the complement systems of individual major word categories in English, the internal structure of phrases and clauses and the classification of complementisers, among other issues of syntax. According to the source, complement order refers to the relative linear ordering (= word order) of the complement (p. 349). The notion of complement ordering is exemplified in the lexical entry for the verb 'give' in (11) below. The lexical entry specifies that the verb 'give' can take both NP and PP complements and that when it does, 'give' occurs first (since it is the head), the NP complement occurs after 'give', and the PP occurs last. The lexical entry for the verb "give", according to the source, is presented in (11).

(11) give: categorial features + V, -N]

Subcategorisation frame [-NP [Pp...to...]

The author formulates the information contained in the lexical entry in (11) into a principle stated in (12) below:

(12) PERIPHERY PRINCIPLE:

The head term of a phrase appears at the periphery of X-bar (p. 350).

Radford (1988) raises a further issue somewhat akin to that about complement order, the issue of the boundedness of complements to their associated heads. This tendency for complements to occur close to their heads, permitting an intervening element/structure, is referred to as "structural affinity" between the head and its complement. This is formulated as a principle tagged "Strict Adjacency Principle", stated by the source as in (13):

(13) STRICT ADJACENCY PRINCIPLE:

An NP complement of a V must be strictly adjacent to V (Radford, p. 988; p. 351). Given that PPs can serve complement or adjunct functions, confusion may arise particularly with regard to complement ordering. The author painstakingly distinguishes between PPs as complements and PPs as adjuncts. Two examples are provided by the author to illustrate thus:

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- (14) (a) [a student [of physics]
NP Np PP
(b) [a student [with long hair]
NP PP

Radford (1988) analyses the PP in (14) (a) as a complement because the PP [of physics] specifies what the student in question is studying, whereas the PP [with long hair] is an adjunct because it merely expresses an additional piece of information about the student. The source also indicates how these two PPs may be ordered relative to the head if they both occurred in the same phrasal (X) structure. Thus, following the principle stated in (12) and (13) above, the complement PP would occur before the Adjunct PP. This ordering principle is stated in the following term as in (15):1:

- (15) (a) Complements expand [X] into X-bar
(b) Adjuncts expand [X]-bar into [X]-bar (p.176)

Radford (1988) thus proposes the phrase structure rules in (16) to capture this prediction.

- (16) (i) → PP Complement Rule
(ii) → X PP (Adjunct Rule) (p.177)

Radford (1997) provides one of the most up-to-date and comprehensive discussions on complementation, complement-selection and the illocutionary force that may be identified with complement material. According to the author, complementation is explicable in terms of a 'sisterhood' relation where the head of a given phrase is analysed as the sister to its complement on account of the fact that they are nodes branching from the same mother node (p. 498). Furthermore, the author defines the relation between a lexical head and its complement in the following formulation:

- (17) A constituent X is the complement of a head H (and, by extension, of an X-bar or HP constituent which is a projection of H) if X and H are sisters and the mother of X is a projection of H (Radford, 1997, p.107).

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Two claims in the above formulation are of interest to the present investigation: One, complements are sisters to heads and daughters of the same mother node. This emphasises the strong bond which exists between the heads of phrases and their complements such that as Aarts (2001) notes, the mobility which adjuncts enjoy over complements cannot dislodge the complement from its bounded position to a head category (*ibid*). Two, complements expand heads into intermediate, phrasal levels (or X-bar). Adjuncts cannot. This instructive understanding of this principle serves as a guide to L2 users of complement – adjunct placement and ordering.

Carnie (2011) draws insights from three of the most popular modern approaches to syntactic analysis: Chomskyan Minimalism (also known as the Minimalist Program or MP), Head-Driven Phrase Structure Grammar (HPSG), and Lexical-Functional Grammar (LFG) in the treatments of various concepts and notions in English syntax. The author provides elaborate discussions and analyses of lexical and functional categories along with their subcategories, such as constituents, MERGE (Complements and Adjuncts), Movement and Control as well as their sub-categories like non-finite constructions, and so on.

The book is not segmented into the traditional chapters, but units. Units 12 and 17 are of immense descriptive benefit to the present study. Carnie (2011, p.12) defines the term “complement” as “the word or phrase that is C-MERGED with the head as required by the heads INTERNAL feature”. This view of a complement is based on the current DP Hypothesis analysis of the traditional NP constituent. According to the DP Hypothesis, the Determiner is the head of the DP (in English for example, *a, an, the /house/ orange, the box, etc.*), and the following noun, its complement.

One major point that can be gleaned from Carnie's (2011) view of complementation is that complements are materials required (=subcategorised for) by head categories and are bound to their related heads because they bear a strong semantic affinity with the heads (cf. Radford, 1988, 1997; Van Valin, 2001; Poole, 2002; Adger, 2003).

Attention in unit 17 of Carnie (2011) is to adjunct as a functional category like the one just discussed. In Carnie's view, adjuncts are modifiers of heads – like complements but unlike the former, “they are not introduced by an INTERNAL or

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EXTERNAL feature”. The adjuncts typically add optional classificatory information” (p.192). The point about the optionality of adjuncts refers to the grammatical relation of a constituent which specifies the *how*, *when*, *where*, or *why* of a situation or state of affairs expressed in a sentence”. Earlier work by Brown and Miller (1980) points out the same features possessed by adjuncts: They are not arguments of verbs; that is, adjuncts are not participants in the event denoted by the verb, hence are more peripheral elements of the propositional structure of a sentence.

Carnie (2011) offers some useful hints on how complement PPs may be distinguished from adjunct PPs thus:

If the head is an N and the modifier is a PP headed by *of*, then the PP is a complement to the N, eg. a book of poems.

If the head is an N and the modifier is a PP headed by other prepositions, then the PP is an adjunct to the Noun, eg., a book with a red cover (p.193).

The source calls for a little caution when dealing with verbs. Thus, for example, DPs and PPs are attested to serve as complements to ditransitive verbs, DPs, PPs and Advps which modifiers are adjuncts. A second component of the subject area of the present investigation is Nigerian English (henceforth NigE), a variety of the English used in Nigeria. Its existence is well established and recognized since after the Ibadan Conference in 1978 and the publication thereafter of the papers deriving from the conference in 1979 in a volume entitled *Varieties and Functions of English in Nigeria*. Expectedly, much work has been done in the area in terms of book contributions like *English Usage: Notable Nigerian Variations* (Kujore, 1985); *Nigerian English Usage: An Introduction* (Jowitt, 1991); *Nigerian English, Phonology: A Preference Grammar* (Ugorji, 2010); and others. Besides the books cited above, there are many articles, MA and PhD reports on the existence, characterisation and variety differentiation of Nigerian English. Furthermore, works by Bamgbose, Afolayan, Adesanonye, Adekunle, Banjo, Akere, Odumuh, Adetugbo, Ayodele, Jibril are classics on Nigerian English studies.

The existence of the works on NigE mentioned above notwithstanding, there is the need to see earlier studies on NigE, especially in the areas related to this study. Of direct relevance to this investigation is Kujore (1985). Appendix II of this work focuses

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on usages related to Lexis and Grammar in Nigerian English, such as adaptation of Idiomatic Fixed Phrases and Proverbial Expressions. Kujore (1985) provides a list of inappropriate use of prepositional heads and juxtaposes Nigerian English usage with Standard British English. The emphasis is on the prepositions which Nigerian English L2 users of English select to head the prepositional phrases (PPs) in their speech/writing. Kujore's (1985) work does not implicate either meaning considerations or functional relations among the constituents which make up phrases/sentences containing them. This is the gap that the present investigation seeks to narrow.

Odumuh (1987) examines some issues in Nigerian English usage, particularly as they have to do with variations, and recommends that an empirical approach be adopted with a view to establishing detailed structures and variations. Attah (2000) states unequivocally that an authentic description of Nigerian English should be based on empirical evidence, as “accurate statistical data from serious scientific studies” will provide adequate descriptions of NigE features. The concerns expressed in Odumuh (1987) and Attah (2000) are partly addressed in this study because even though a corpus-based approach is not adopted; however, by adopting a qualitative and quantitative approach in collecting and analysing data, objectivity, reliability and validity are ensured.

Regarding prepositional use by Nigerian L2 speakers of English, Adesanonye (1970) and Jowitt (1991) observe similar trends: omission. This has been accounted for by the fact of L1 transfer: most Nigerian languages do not have as many prepositions in their lexical store as English does. The result, therefore, is for the L2 user to omit prepositions where, in English, they should occur.

Similarly, Udoudom (2011) studied Ibibio-English speakers' handling of complement selection in respect of some nouns and verbs in English and observed variations in the complement PP selection of N- and V- heads of British English and educated Nigerian English. The study further revealed that the variations observed were occasioned by violations of the selection restrictions which relevant N- and V-heads in English impose on P-heads of complement PPs. Udo0udom (2011) agrees with Kujore (1985) even though the former adopts a qualitative and quantitative approach to the study.

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Methodology

The data analysed in this study were elicited; they were based on responses to three grammaticality judgement intuition tasks administered to 450 Nigerians of varying socio-economic backgrounds selected through a stratified random sampling method. The subjects were selected from among university undergraduates of English and university graduates with BA, B.Sc., MA and Ph.D., using education as a major criterion for stratification. Justification for this was based on the fact that these subjects were considered to have had a long enough/adequate exposure to the English language and could discern the functional distinctions of PPs in English.

Subjects' grammaticality intuition was tested using three tests. Test I was coded as the Structure Recognition Test (SRT), intended to test subjects' ability in identifying English propositional phrases. Twenty sentences were provided by the researcher, and the subjects were required to identify strings/groups of words which are PPs. Text II coded FDT (Function Determination Test) sought to measure subjects' ability in determining the grammatical functions of the PPs identified in Test I. The third test, coded C-AOT (Complement-Adjunct Ordering Test), was designed to test subjects' ability in ordering complement PPs and adjunct PPs appropriately.

Theoretical Framework: The X-bar Theory

The X-bar theory is a component of Government Binding (GB) devised by Chomsky (1970). It handles the relationship between the head of a phrase and the other elements which occur with it within the phrasal structure. The head of a phrase is described as "semantically [the] most important" element in the structure of a phrase. It is the lexical item around which the phrase is built. The head constituent determines the choice of its complement. Within the X-bar system of analysis, 'X' is a symbol which represents any of the major lexical categories Noun (N), Verb (V), Adjective (Adj) and Preposition (P).

One major characteristic of the X-bar format is that it recognises the existence of intermediate structures larger than the lexical head but smaller than the full phrase. For example, the string "female hostel" consists of the head noun 'hostel' and its projection "female hostel". The structure is analysed within the X-bar system as N-bar or N-single bar, that is one level projection (or expansion) of the noun head. It is an intermediate-

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level expansion of the head in question. However, if the determiner “the” is added to the structure, it would represent a second-level expansion of the head “hostel”. The resultant structure, “the female hostel”, is then regarded as the full noun phrase (NP) or, to use the appropriate technical terminology, the maximal projection of the N (Jackendoff, 1977; Radford, 1988; 1997; Clark, 1990).

The principles of X-bar postulate that all phrases in all natural languages have the same structure of heads, specifiers and complements. Surface physical manifestations of lexical phrases are, in actual fact, projections from the lexical specification of the particular lexical item acting as head. The sketch of phrasal structure outlined above can be represented diagrammatically as in the figure below:

Figure 2: Structure of a Phrase, Adapted from Adger

Figure 3: The X-bar Format/Theory

The X-bar system recognises functional categories like inflection or I as head of inflection phrase (IP or I'' or I-double bar and I' and I single bar, Tense Phrase (TP), and Agreement phrase (AgrP). Moreover, the analysis of embedded subordinate clauses and the position/attachment of adjunct material can be assimilated to the X-bar format; hence, the X-bar system presents the following categories:

- (1) (a) X (with no bars is the same as a lexical head, N, V, A or P
- (b) B-bar (or X' or X single bar) corresponds to a double bar projection or minimal phrase, of a lexical item, e.g. N-bar (N' or N or N-single bar).
- (c) X-double bar (or X'' or X) corresponds to a triple level expansion of the lexical head. It is the full phrase of maximal projection, e.g. N'' , N-double bar.

The X-bar system of analysis provides a more well-articulated method of representing the structure of phrases in natural languages. Its major advantage over phrase structure lies in its ability to account for intermediate phrasal structures as well as functional phrases; its system of analysis generates the head constituent in a phrase and shows the placement of the head's accompanying material, thereby making apparent the function of such material as a complement or adjunct (Radford, 1988; Jackendoff, 1977; Carnie, 2007). Using relevant rules, the X-bar format appropriately delineates bar-level projections and the function and other accompanying materials relative to the head in a phrase (XP). In this study, the distinction between similarly structured phrases like Complement-Adjunct PPs and the focus of this study are well established.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 The present study focused attention on the following:

- i. determining the ability of the subjects studied in identifying Prepositional Phrases (PPs) a structural unit in sentences of English;
- ii. determining the ability of the subjects studied in differentiating between adjunct PPs and complement PPs given that they are of the same schematic form: $PP \rightarrow P + NP$; and
- iii. determining subjects' ability in ordering adjunct PPs and complement PPs appropriately.

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As indicated in the methodology subsection, data for this study were obtained from the subjects using three grammaticality judgement intuition tasks, which sought to determine the subjects' linguistic knowledge of the aspect of syntax investigated: the distinction between adjunct PPs and complement PPs. Results of the tests are presented in the tables following: Table 1 shows the subjects' performance in the Structure Recognition Test (SRT); Table 2 contains results for subjects' performance in the Function Determination Test (FDT); and in Table 3, results for ordering adjunct-complement PPs are presented.

Table 1: Subjects' Performance in Structure Recognition Test

S/N	Item Tested	No Able	% Able	No Not Able	% Not Able
1	The book [of poems] with a red cover	207	46%	243	54%
2.	The basket [of fruits] [from the village]	315	46%	137	30.4%
3.	The chief [of staff] in the presidency	308	68%	142	32%
4.	He sits [in a chair] by the window	287	64%	163	36%
5.	Angela washed the plates [in the bathroom]	324	72%	126	28%
6.	Men [of the Jungun tribe]	189	42%	261	58%
7.	A teacher [of English]	326	72.4%	124	27.5
8.	The president [of Nigeria]	322	72.1	128	28.4
9.	The president -presented his speech [in a rush]	285	63.3	165	36.6
10.	The broadcast crew met [outside the studio]	281	62.4	169	37.5
11.	The chef cut the meat [with a butcher's knife]	225	50%	225	50
12.	The senators hold a meeting [before plenary]	310	68.8	140	31.1

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13.	He looked [at the picture] and signed [in awe] adjunct	210	46.7	240	53.3
14	The chairman queried their insistence [on the arrangement	211	46.8	239	53.1
15.	I eat beans [with a fork]	261	58%	189	42%
16.	He carried the animal home [on his shoulders]	272	60.4%	178	39.5
17.	Dara will bake the cake [for the party]	267	61.3%	183	40.6
18.	The governor commended his specialization [in shoemaking]	268	57.3	192	42.6
19.	The decision was taken [in our party congress] [on Tuesdays]	210	46.6	240	53.3
20.	John washed the plates [in the bathroom]	276	61.3	174	38.6

Table 2: Subjects' Performance in Function Determination Test

S/N	Item Tested	No Able	% Able	No Not Able	% Not Able
1	He sits in a chair by the window	108	24%	342	75.5
2.	The basket of fruits from the village	119	26.4	331	73.5
3.	The book of poems with a red cover	210	46.6	240	53.3%
4.	The chief of staff in the presidency	162	36%	288	64%
5.	He is a student from Nigeria in Columbia	96	21.3	354	78.6
6.	George looked at the picture in awe	127	28.2	232	71.7
7.	Eunice might be going to the mall on Saturday	132	29.3	318	70.6

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8.	They sing in the choir at Christmas	121	26.8	329	73.1%
9.	John stood by the door at the office	113	25.1	337	74.8%
10.	The decision was taken in our party congress on Tuesday	149	33.1	301	66.8

Table 3: Performance in Complement-Adjunct Ordering

S/N	Item Tested	No Able	% Able	No Not Able	% Not Able
1	He sits by the window in a chair	68	15.1	382	84.4
2.	The basket from the village of fruits	128	28.4	322	71.5
3.	The chief in the presidency of staff	146	32.4	304	67.5
4.	Eunice might be going on Saturday to the mall	56	12.4	394	87.5
5.	He is a student in Columbia from Nigeria	52	11.5	398	88.4
6.	They sing at Christmas in the choir	86	19.1	364	80.8
7.	John stood at the office by the door	67	14.8	383	85.1
8.	The decision was taken on Tuesday in our party congress	80	17.7	370	82.2
9.	George looked in awe at the picture	53	11.7	397	88.2
10.	The book with a red cover of poems	128	28.4	322	71.5

4.2 Discussion

The results in Table 1 show that the subjects studied could identify the structural unit known as the prepositional phrase (PP) in English. Evidence for this generalisation is shown in the high performance recorded in most of the items tested. As is apparent from the table under reference, no item recorded fewer than 150 subjects who were able. In some test items, for example, item 7, as many as 326 subjects, representing 72%, were

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able. Test item 5 also recorded a high score, as 324 subjects representing 72% of the population studied exhibited ability.

The cognitive salience demonstrated by the subjects observed in this task can be accounted for by their linguistic knowledge of the structure of a prepositional phrase in English; that is, the fact that English prepositional phrases are structured out of a preposition which is the head and a following NP and so have the schematic form (10):

(10) PP → P+NP

This observation is supported by the ability of the subjects to identify PPs even in test items which contain two PPs like items 1, 3, 4, 5 and 20. As shown in Table 1, ten (10) prepositions feature in the test: *at, by, before, from, for, in, of, outside* and *with*, each heading a PP which serves either complement or adjunct function yet, subjects who were able, identified them appropriately as the structural unit, PP.

The high facilitation indices recorded in the Structure Recognition Test (SRT) presented in Table 1 have further implications for the cognitive salience of the subjects studied. It implicates their knowledge of phrase structure, which, within the X-bar format, is held to be made up of a head constituent and other linguistic elements technically known as 'specifier' and 'complement' (Chomsky, 1970; Jackendoff, 1977). It is on the strength of this knowledge that subjects who were able, could identify PPs as groups of words, not as individual lexical items.

Regarding the performance of subjects classified as "Not Able", two factors may be used to account for their inability: (1) the lexical store of languages is not the same. For instance, *Ibibio*, a Lower-Cross language has only two prepositions – *kē* and *yé* with *mme* as a variant of *yé* (Essien, 1990; Udoudom, 2006), while English has several. It follows therefore that subjects in the studied population who are *Ibibio*, were not likely to know/recognise many prepositions in English neither were they likely to possess the linguistic competence to enable them know that prepositions can subcategorise for complements like verbs, nouns and adjectives, as current formats of syntactic analysis indicate (cf Haegeman, 1994; Radford, 1997; Adger, 2001; Aarts, 2001, etc.).

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The second factor has to do with individual language users' developmental difficulties: individual users of relevant L₂ have peculiar problems in using certain aspects of an L₂. This is sometimes traceable to their model(s), ... and so on.

Table 2 shows results for the Function Determination Test (FDT), which required subjects to distinguish between complement PPs and adjunct PPs. As is apparent, there is a general lack of intuitive knowledge about the functions which PPs in English can realise. The test items in Table 2 numbered 1-10 are sentences which have similar constituent structure: Each contains two PPs, with each PP serving as a complement or an adjunct role. The first occurring PP realises the complement function, while the second, adjunct function. In Test item 1 of Table 2, 108 subjects could assign the PPs their appropriate function. This represents 24% of the entire population studied. 342 subjects representing 75.5% of the population were not able to state the function each of the PPs fills. The highest "Number Able" is 210 out of 450, representing 46.6%, and the second highest is 162, recorded for test item 4, with a calculated percentage of 36%. The performance index for subjects classified as "Able" ranges from 21.3% to 46.6%, whereas the calculated percentages for those classified under "Number not Able" range from 53% (lowest) to 78.6%.

The general poor performance in the Function Determination Test (FDT) speaks of subjects' lack of grammaticality judgement intuition about other major word categories like nouns, adjectives and prepositions being capable of taking complements. Consequent upon this, the subjects studied may not have associated complement and adjunct functions with nominal heads, as is the case in test items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5, which have the nouns "chair", "basket", "book", "chief" and "student" as head categories.

Similarly, the adjunct function appears to be associated more with verbs than with nouns, adjectives and prepositions. However, more current formats of analysis of the structure of phrases in English (like the X-bar format used in this study) show that nouns can be specified by determiners and can subcategorise for complements like verbs (see Fig. 1 above).

Regarding the verbs 'heads' which featured in the test items, the subjects tended to associate the complement function more with nouns/nominals and adjectives than

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with PPs and the adjunct function more with single-word adverbs, not with PPs. This has usage implications in nonnative contexts, as the non-distinction of complement and adjunct PPs will inhibit the performance of Nigerian L2 users of English. Thus, they are not likely to be able to specify meaning in discourse nor be able to place/position adjunct PPs appropriately, a situation which can hinder communication/affect intelligibility.

Table 3 shows results of Test III, which sought subjects' grammatical judgement intuition about the ordering of complement and adjunct PPs given that word order considerations are significant in meaning determination (cf. Finegan, 2012).

As is apparent from the readings on Table 3, the subjects performed fairly well in three of the ten test items of the task: 2, 3 and 10, in which over a hundred subjects were "able". 128 subjects could reorder the PPs in Test item 2 appropriately. This number represents 28.4% of the population studied; 146 subjects were "able" in test item 3, representing 32%, and 128 subjects were "able" in test item 10, representing 28.4%. The seeming fair performances may be attributed to the subject's intuitive knowledge of the structure of sentences in English. Following this, the subjects know that "of phrases", such as we have in the sentences under consideration, should occur after the noun heads "basket" in test item 2, "chief" in 3 and "book" in 10, not sentence finally.

In Test items 1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9, subjects' inability in ordering the relevant PPs appropriately demonstrates their lack of intuitive linguistic knowledge of the grammatical functions which the structural elements of a language can fill. The two PPs in each of the sentences serve either a complement function or an adjunct one. By the Word Order (WO) principles of English, complements are bound to their heads because they are the semantic objects of their respective heads (cf. Carnie, 2007). Thus, in the context of this investigation, PPs which serve complement functions are to be ordered close to their heads because they are sisters of X (Head) and daughters of X/ (i.e., the first level projection of the Head).

As may be gleaned from Table 3, each of the N- and V- heads subcategorises for complements realisable by PPs. In test item 1, the PP "in a chair" is the complement of the V-head "sits"; therefore, it should occur closer to it than the PP "by the window", which in this context is an adjunct. 68 subjects representing 15.1% of the population could reorder the two PPs appropriately.

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Subjects' performance in test items 4, 5 and 9 further demonstrates their lack of grammaticality judgement intuition regarding the ordering of complement and adjunct PPs, relative to lexical heads. Test item 4 has the V-head “might be going”, and its complement should be the PP “to the mall” positioned close to it, while the PP “on Saturday” is the adjunct occurring after the complement. “Student” is the noun head in test item 5, the PP “from Nigeria” is its complement and “in Colombia” the adjunct...and so on. A look at the number of subjects "able" in respect of these items shows 56 subjects representing 12.4% for test item 4, 52 representing 11.5% for item 5 and 53% only representing 11.7% for item 9. These statistics indicate a general inability of the subjects studied to distinguish between the complement function of PPs and their adjunct function.

Conclusion

In all, this paper presented results and offered a discussion about the performance of educated Nigerian speakers of English in distinguishing between adjunct and complement PPs in relevant syntactic contexts. In this discussion, we mapped the structural element PP unto the functional roles which they may realise.

This research uncovers for the L2 user of English the fact that the structural elements of a language have semantic correlates and that Word Order (WO) contributes to meaning determination in sentences. It was illustrated how knowledge of phrase structure alone contributes little to the construction of grammatical sentences in English. By examining the performance of the subjects studied in the function determination of PPs in English and the ordering of PPs according to function, this paper illustrated how subjects exhibited incompetence both in knowing which of the grammatical functions – adjunct or complement – PPs may realise. In particular, the results and discussion demonstrate that the subjects lack knowledge of structural-functional correlations.

This study also shows that the diversity in the L1 lexical store of L2 users of English impacts their performance. It was demonstrated that the subjects were not familiar with some prepositions which head some PPs in the tasks responded to. Furthermore, the subjects tended to associate headness with verbs, not with nouns.

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By investigating L2 speakers of English and seeking their grammaticality judgement intuition on this aspect of syntax, the paper contributes to our understanding of the form-meaning relationships which exist among the elements of a language, in particular of how language is a very highly organised system of communication such that although there may be formal variants, the organising principles of particular languages ensure appropriate ordering of linguistic elements.

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